

Importance of Nari Shakti to Achieve Viksit Bharat 2047

¹Dr. Thiruppathi KTM, Assistant Professor, AMET Business School,
AMET University, Chennai

²Mr. S.Prithvi, Assistant Professor, AMET Business School,
AMER University, Chennai

Abstract

The vision of *Viksit Bharat 2047* represents India's aspiration to become a developed nation by the 100th anniversary of its independence. Central to this vision is the empowerment of women, or *Nari Shakti*, which encompasses the immense potential of nearly half of India's population. Women have historically been the backbone of India's progress, contributing significantly across various fields. However, systemic challenges have often curtailed their full participation. This paper delves into the multifaceted role of women in nation-building, emphasizing areas like education, entrepreneurship, political governance, and social reforms. It identifies barriers to women's empowerment, examines government initiatives and legislative frameworks, and highlights success stories, while proposing actionable strategies for leveraging *Nari Shakti* to achieve inclusive and sustainable development.

Keywords: Nari Shakti, Viksit Bharat, Developed India, Women Power, Women Entrepreneurship, Women Leadership, Political, Policy Making

Introduction

India's development story has been marked by significant achievements, yet disparities in gender equality persist. Women constitute nearly 48% of the population and represent an unparalleled resource for achieving holistic growth. As India marches toward 2047, the role of women will be critical in shaping a society that is inclusive, prosperous, and equitable. Empowering women goes beyond moral or ethical imperatives; it is a pragmatic approach to enhancing economic productivity, reducing poverty, and building a cohesive society. This paper explores the intersections of gender equality and national development, focusing on how *Nari Shakti* can catalyze progress toward *Viksit Bharat*.

1. Role of Nari Shakti in Nation-Building

1.1 Economic Contribution

Women contribute significantly to India's economy through their participation in agriculture, industries, and the informal sector. Despite systemic barriers, women are pivotal in driving micro-enterprises, cottage industries, and rural economic initiatives. In recent years, women entrepreneurs have emerged as catalysts of innovation, particularly in startups, e-commerce, and green technologies. Empowering women economically has a multiplier effect, as it enhances household incomes, improves child welfare, and stimulates community development.

1.2 Education and Skill Development

Education is a cornerstone for empowerment. Increasing female literacy has been linked to improved economic outcomes and societal progress. Vocational training and STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education can enable women to enter high-

growth industries. Women skilled in emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and renewable energy, will be instrumental in shaping the future economy.

1.3 Political Participation

Political empowerment is critical for inclusive governance. Women's representation in local self-government, facilitated by reservation policies, has brought transformative changes to rural governance. However, their participation in higher political echelons remains limited. Increasing women's presence in legislative and decision-making bodies will ensure that policies are more representative and equitable.

2. Challenges Faced by Women

2.1 Socio-Cultural Barriers

Patriarchal norms, gender-based stereotypes, and cultural restrictions continue to impede women's progress. Practices like early marriage, unequal inheritance rights, and restricted mobility limit women's potential.

2.2 Economic Challenges

Wage disparity remains a pressing issue, with women earning significantly less than their male counterparts. Limited access to financial resources, credit, and property ownership restricts women's ability to invest in businesses or education.

2.3 Safety and Security

India has one of the highest incidences of violence against women, including domestic violence, harassment, and human trafficking. Despite legal protections, enforcement mechanisms often fall short, leaving many women vulnerable.

3. Government and Policy Interventions

3.1 Key Schemes and Initiatives

1. **Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (BBBP)**
Launched in 2015, BBBP addresses the declining child sex ratio and promotes the education and empowerment of girls. The scheme operates on three pillars: advocacy campaigns for gender equality, strengthening girl child survival, and promoting education through community-level engagement. By addressing social norms and enhancing access to education, BBBP has fostered positive change in previously underserved regions.
2. **Stand-Up India and Mudra Yojana**
These initiatives are pivotal for economic empowerment. **Stand-Up India** provides bank loans to women entrepreneurs in the non-farm sector, helping them establish small businesses. Similarly, **Mudra Yojana** enables access to microfinance, empowering women to become self-reliant. Together, these schemes address financial barriers and enable women's participation in economic activities, particularly in rural areas.

3. Mission Shakti and Mahila E-Haat

- **Mission Shakti** integrates safety, security, and empowerment initiatives for women, focusing on capacity building, livelihood generation, and entrepreneurship.
- **Mahila E-Haat**, a digital marketing platform, connects women entrepreneurs with a larger market. It promotes financial independence by eliminating intermediaries and enhancing access to buyers.

3.2 Legislative Measures

1. **Prohibition of Child Marriage Act (2006)**
This act prohibits marriage below the age of 18 for girls and 21 for boys, combating early marriage practices and promoting the rights of girls to education and personal development.
2. **Equal Remuneration Act (1976)**
The act mandates equal pay for equal work, regardless of gender. This legislation addresses wage disparities and promotes gender equity in workplaces.
3. **Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace Act (2013)**
This act ensures safe and secure workplaces for women. By defining and penalizing harassment, it has empowered women to report incidents without fear of retribution.
4. **Reservation Policies for Women**
The reservation of seats for women in Panchayati Raj institutions has increased their participation in local governance, fostering grassroots-level leadership and ensuring that policies reflect community needs.

3.3 Global Collaborations

1. **Alignment with UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**
India's focus on Goal 5 (Gender Equality) aligns with its domestic strategies to empower women. This collaboration emphasizes gender parity in education, health, and economic participation, directly contributing to national and global development objectives.
2. **Partnerships with International Organizations**
India works with UN agencies, World Bank, and NGOs to implement gender-focused projects. For instance, the collaboration with UNICEF has strengthened child and maternal health programs, benefiting millions of women.

4. Impact of Nari Shakti on Key Sectors

4.1 Healthcare

Women are central to India's healthcare system, with roles ranging from nurses and midwives to Accredited Social Health Activists (ASHAs). Initiatives like the Ayushman Bharat scheme have highlighted the importance of women in implementing public health measures. Empowering women through education and training in healthcare professions can address critical gaps in maternal and child health, vaccination drives, and disease prevention campaigns.

4.2 Education

Women educators shape the future of communities, particularly in rural and marginalized areas. They often act as change agents, encouraging girls to pursue higher education. Policies promoting leadership roles for women in academia, scholarships for girls, and incentives for female teachers have proven effective in bridging educational disparities.

4.3 Technology and Innovation

Despite underrepresentation, women have made significant strides in technology. Initiatives such as **Digital India** have provided opportunities for women to upskill in tech fields, participate in online entrepreneurship, and access digital resources. Promoting STEM education and mentorship programs can further boost women's representation in leadership roles within emerging industries like artificial intelligence and biotechnology.

4.4 Environment and Sustainability

Women have historically been custodians of natural resources. Movements like **Chipko** and community forestry initiatives demonstrate their role in conserving ecosystems. Today, women lead climate adaptation programs, solar energy projects, and organic farming initiatives, showcasing their potential to drive sustainable development.

5. Case Studies and Success Stories

5.1 Women Leaders in Business and Politics

1. **Kiran Mazumdar-Shaw**, founder of Biocon, is a global pioneer in biotechnology. Her journey exemplifies how women can break barriers and lead innovative enterprises.
2. In politics, **Pratibha Patil**, the first woman President of India, symbolizes the ability of women to lead at the highest levels. Her tenure focused on social welfare and gender equality.

5.2 Grassroots Movements

Women-led grassroots movements, like the **Self-Employed Women's Association (SEWA)**, have transformed communities by organizing women in informal sectors. These movements empower women economically while addressing issues like healthcare, education, and housing.

5.3 Community Impact of Self-Help Groups (SHGs)

SHGs, such as those under the **Kudumbashree Mission** in Kerala, provide financial resources and a support network for women. By pooling resources and sharing knowledge, SHGs enhance financial independence and foster a sense of collective empowerment.

6. Strategies to Harness Nari Shakti

Achieving the full potential of *Nari Shakti* requires a multipronged approach that addresses systemic challenges and fosters a conducive environment for women's growth and contribution. This section outlines key strategies involving policy reform, social change, and technological empowerment.

6.1 Policy Recommendations

1. Education and Skilling

Education is the cornerstone of empowerment. A focused approach to education and skill development can enhance women's participation in high-growth industries.

- **Expand programs offering scholarships for girls in STEM fields:** Encouraging girls to pursue education in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) is essential for bridging the gender gap in high-tech fields. Scholarships and mentorship programs targeted at girls from rural and underserved areas can inspire them to enter traditionally male-dominated sectors such as IT, robotics, and space exploration.
- **Establish vocational training centres focusing on emerging technologies:** The rapid evolution of industries like artificial intelligence, machine learning, and renewable energy demands specialized skills. Setting up vocational training hubs at the district level, with a focus on cutting-edge technologies, can prepare women for employment in these fields. Public-private partnerships can further enhance the reach and effectiveness of such centres.

2. Gender-Sensitive Governance

Integrating gender considerations into governance structures ensures inclusivity and better representation of women's interests.

- **Ensure gender mainstreaming in policymaking processes:** All government policies and programs should incorporate a gender lens to address the unique challenges women face. For example, budget allocations for health, education, and employment should include specific provisions for women-centric programs.
- **Promote women's leadership in public and private institutions:** Introducing quotas or incentives for women in leadership roles across sectors can normalize their presence in decision-making positions. Leadership training programs and networking opportunities can also enhance their readiness for such roles.

6.2 Social Reforms

1. Awareness Campaigns

Changing societal attitudes and dismantling stereotypes is crucial for long-term gender equality.

- **Challenge gender stereotypes through mass media and grassroots outreach programs:** Campaigns using television, radio, and social media can highlight the achievements of women in various fields, challenging traditional gender roles. Grassroots initiatives, such as street plays and community dialogues, can reinforce these messages in rural areas.

- **Educate communities about the benefits of women's economic and social participation:**
Highlighting the economic and social advantages of women's active involvement in the workforce, governance, and education can encourage families and communities to support their aspirations.

2. Family Support Systems

A supportive family environment is integral to enabling women's professional and personal growth.

- **Create affordable childcare facilities to support working mothers:**
The lack of accessible childcare is a significant barrier to women's participation in the workforce. Establishing subsidized childcare centres near workplaces and residential areas can help mothers balance their professional and familial responsibilities.
- **Implement parental leave policies encouraging shared responsibilities between parents:**
Introducing paternity leave alongside maternity leave can challenge traditional caregiving norms and promote shared responsibilities. This reform fosters a more balanced family dynamic and reduces the burden on women.

6.3 Technological Empowerment

Technology can be a powerful enabler for women's empowerment, providing access to education, employment, and entrepreneurship opportunities.

1. Digital Literacy

Bridging the digital divide is essential to ensure that women, especially in rural areas, can leverage technology for their benefit.

- **Conduct digital literacy camps for rural women, enabling them to access government schemes and financial tools:**
Training programs tailored to women can teach basic computer and smartphone skills, enabling them to use e-governance portals, online banking, and digital marketplaces. These camps can also introduce them to mobile apps for health, agriculture, and education.

2. Encouraging Innovation

Women's involvement in innovation drives economic growth and fosters inclusive development.

- **Set up innovation hubs in collaboration with educational institutions to promote women-led startups in tech:**
Establishing women-centric innovation hubs at universities and colleges can nurture entrepreneurial talent. These hubs can provide incubation facilities, mentorship, and funding to women entrepreneurs developing innovative solutions in fields like aggrotech, fintech, and clean energy.

- **Provide grants and mentorship for women in R&D-focused industries:** Grants targeting women researchers and innovators can increase their participation in fields like biotechnology, pharmaceuticals, and space exploration. Pairing financial assistance with mentorship opportunities ensures long-term success.

Conclusion

As India aspires to achieve *Viksit Bharat 2047*, *Nari Shakti* will be instrumental in driving this transformation. Investing in women's education, healthcare, and economic participation can unleash their potential, leading to inclusive and sustainable development. Collaborative efforts among governments, businesses, and civil society are essential to create an environment where women can thrive. The empowerment of women will not only shape a prosperous India but also redefine the nation's identity on the global stage.

References

1. Government of India. (2023). *Mission Shakti Guidelines*. Ministry of Women and Child Development.
2. United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2021). *Gender Equality and Development Goals*.
3. World Economic Forum. (2022). *Global Gender Gap Report*.
4. Niti Aayog. (2023). *India @100: Roadmap for Inclusive Growth*.
5. Bose, S. (2022). *Women Entrepreneurs in India: Opportunities and Challenges*. Indian Journal of Economics and Development.